

Exploitation Plan Outline

MARIS

Dick M.A. Schaap

AQUARIUS has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme for Research and Innovation under grant agreement No 101130915. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

About this document

Title	D7.2 - Exploitation Plan Outline
Work Package	WP7, Impact: Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
Lead Partner	MARIS
Lead Author (Org)	Dick M.A. Schaap (MARIS)
Contributing Author(s)	Oonagh McMeel (SSBE), Nathalie Tonne (SSBE), Bernadette Ni Chongaile (MI), Frank Armstrong (MI)
Reviewers	Sissy Iona (HCMR)
Due Date	30.04.2025
Submission Date	30.04.2025
Version	1

Dissemination Level

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PU: Public
<input type="checkbox"/>	PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission)
<input type="checkbox"/>	RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission)
<input type="checkbox"/>	CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)

AQUARIUS: Aqua Research Infrastructure Services for the health and protection of our unique, oceans, seas and freshwater ecosystems is a Research and Innovation action (RIA) funded by the Horizon Europe Work programme topics addressed: HORIZON-INFRA-2023-SERV-01-01 - Research infrastructure services to enable R&I addressing main challenges and EU priorities. Start date: 01 March 2024. End date: 29 February 2028.

Funded by
the European Union

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

ADD	- AQUARIUS Dataflow Dashboard
DTO	- Digital Twin of the Oceans
KER	- Key Exploitable Result
NODC	- National Oceanographic Data Centre
RI	- Research Infrastructure
R&I	- Research & Innovation
SME	- Small Medium Enterprise
TA	- Transnational Access
TG	- Target Group

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1. Summary

This document constitutes the AQUARIUS 'Exploitation Plan Outline' as Deliverable D7.2. This document builds on the AQUARIUS Communication and Dissemination Plan (D7.1), which identifies target audiences and dissemination channels and tools for promoting the AQUARIUS project and its results. It also builds upon the AQUARIUS Data Management Strategy (D6.2) which will be deployed to ensure that all metadata and data, gathered and generated by TA projects, will be managed in line with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable).

This document provides an outline for the planned content of the final AQUARIUS Exploitation Plan (D7.3) and how this content will be collected and compiled working together with the TA research project teams and relevant Work Package leaders.

An overview is given of potential Key Exploitable Results (KERs), whereby a distinction is made of KERs, related to the TA research projects, and KERs, related to specific Project Work Packages and/or Project Partners. For gathering input during the project, use will be made of templates that will set out clear pathways towards exploitation of each KER beyond the project end. These templates are included as annexes to this document.

The implementation of the exploitation strategy will be integrated with activities for communication and dissemination (WP7) and data management (WP6).

The identification of KERs and their possible exploitation pathways for TA research projects will start once contracts have been signed with the scientific teams that have successfully applied for TA research projects. This will coincide with the activities as planned for refining the initial Data Management Plans of each TA research project in dialogue with the Principal Investigators (PIs) and their research teams.

During the deployment of TA research projects, further coaching will be given for achieving proper implementation of the data management activities. This will also facilitate refining and supporting the exploitation pathways, which should lead to individual exploitation plans that will be bundled as part of the final AQUARIUS Exploitation Plan (D7.3) by M48. Intellectual Property (IP) management will be considered where relevant.

For the project as a whole, key performance indicators have been formulated related to project outputs, which will depend on successful implementation of the WP6 and WP7 activities in cooperation with the TA research teams and selected Work Packages - instrumental for achieving the planned output.

2. Introduction

Communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities are important for achieving a successful project, particularly given the increased focus that the Horizon Europe programme places on activities which demonstrate and maximise the scientific, the societal and economic impact of Research and Innovation (R&I) funding. In the AQUARIUS project, these activities are planned to be implemented through an integrated strategic approach, which is fully embedded in the project's work plan.

Communication activities, aimed to promote the project itself and its success, as well as the dissemination and exploitation of results together with the management of intellectual assets should be key components. Their successful implementation will bring EU-funded research and its results to the attention of multiple audiences, thus helping to contribute to the expected impacts and outcomes which will address the strategic objectives of Horizon Europe.

Exploitation in the context of Horizon Europe refers to the utilization of project results for further scientific, commercial, societal, or policy purposes. In that context, the AQUARIUS exploitation plan should detail:

- The key exploitable results (KER)
- Target users (who can exploit the results)
- Pathway to users (dissemination channel)
- Impact as a result of the user exploiting the result (KPI/monitoring).
- IP management

This document will give an outline for the planned content of the final AQUARIUS Exploitation Plan (D7.3) and how this content will be collected and compiled working together with the TA research project teams and relevant Work Package leaders.

3. Target Groups

Achieving maximum impact will be organised in AQUARIUS by means of an integrated strategic approach for communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities. Communication and dissemination of the project activities and its results will be directed to **5** main **Target User Groups (TGs)**, namely:

1. Research scientists and Academia (TG1),
2. Relevant EU RIs, long term EU data services and EU Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO) (TG2),
3. Industrial communities and SMEs (TG3),
4. Policy platforms and decision makers (TG4),
5. Wider society including citizen science groups (TG5).

The primary route of dissemination to **Research Scientists & Academia (TG 1)** will be through **training activities** (WP5, WP6), which will be geared at building capacity amongst next generation researchers in the use of (new) Transnational Access services and infrastructure, as well as on harnessing the potential of web based Open Science through FAIR data management and effective use of virtual research environments (i.e., Blue-Cloud) for (big) data analytics. An AQUARIUS online training repository will be set up (WP5), to allow for wider, sustained dissemination of resources beyond the project end. Further dissemination to TG1 will be through **publications** in peer reviewed literature, as a requirement set forth in the calls for TA projects, as well as via **open science platforms** and **catalogues**, such as Zenodo and the Blue-Cloud catalogue, which will enable wider dissemination of TA project results (e.g., new data, new analytical methods) amongst multidisciplinary research communities through its connection with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

AQUARIUS will interact with relevant **EU RIs** and **long-term EU data services** (TG2) in multiple ways throughout the project. They have already been engaged in the co-design of the portfolio of the services that are to be made available to users. They will also be involved in further discussions about exploitation pathways for new data generated through enhanced TA opportunities. Key data services (e.g., SeaDataNet) and long-term EU initiatives (Copernicus Marine, EMODnet, EDITO) will contribute to disseminate and benefit from new data flows through enhanced FAIR data management, to inform key policy processes and in support of Ocean Literacy applications.

Dissemination to **Industry & SMEs** (TG3), **Citizen science Groups** (TG5) and to **Policy & Decision Makers** (TG4) will be achieved through targeted **meetings, workshops, and events**, including a **Final Event**, aiming for participants with representation across all TGs. A video will be produced capturing key messages, for further dissemination and legacy after Project-end.

Dissemination will also be directed to **non-expert, wider society audiences** (TG5) via a variety of routes, including recommending potential uptake of data layers of AQUARIUS by the **European Atlas of the Seas** and outreach via relevant EU initiatives, such as EU4OceanPlatform, Youth4Ocean and the Network of European Blue Schools.

4. AQUARIUS Key Exploitable Results

AQUARIUS identifies two levels of KER as follows:

1. KER resulting from the AQUARIUS project itself (e.g. scientific knowledge in the form of reports, policy briefs, data management plan, best practice guidelines).
2. KER resulting from the funded Transnational Access (TA) research projects (e.g. new data, data products, scientific papers).

At the time of writing this document, the first TA Call has been issued, and the evaluation process is ongoing. Therefore, it is not possible to detail already fully the types of KER arising from the projects. However, this will be resolved once the contracts for the TA research projects have been signed, which will then allow for dialogues with the PIs to discuss their potential KERs.

Following the AQUARIUS proposal and assessing the current project status, the following Key Exploitable Results are considered as potential KERs. However, these will be refined during the project in cooperation with the PIs of the TA research projects, and with leaders and partners in Work Packages.

Work Package	Output	Exploitation Path	Lead
WP6 WP3	1 report on "data gaps" from perspective of current data holdings in leading repositories (D6.1) 1 report on "call priorities" from perspectives of EU directives and missions (D3.1)	Key conclusions have been considered for the formulation of calls for TA projects and will further feed into WP7 Policy Brief, including recommendations towards the future EU Green Deal Data Space.	IFREMER SYKE

WP6	1 overarching Data Management Approach (D6.2) which is adopted in Data Management Plans for each funded TA research project	FAIR Data becomes available in leading marine data management infrastructures (SeaDataNet, EurOBIS, ELIXIR-ENA, ICOS-Ocean, and Copernicus INSTAC), feeding generation of high-quality data products and collections in Copernicus Marine, EMODnet, and EU DTO scenarios (EDITO).	MARIS OGS
WP3	Operational Reports for the 10 “super integration” Transnational Access projects implemented	Lessons learned brought into Exploitation Plan (D7.3)	AWI
WP3 WP4 WP6 WP7	10+ “super integration” Transnational Access projects implemented	Exploitation of KERs described, characterised, and planned in Exploitation Plan (D7.3)	MARIS OGS
WP6	Final report on Data Management achievements and lessons learned (D6.7)	Results of applying the overall Data Management Approach and lessons learned will be documented, while data and metadata from the TA research project should be accessible from the European MDM infrastructures via the AQUARIUS Data Dashboard (ADD).	MARIS
WP3	A European Call Management System (INTERACCESS) for AQUARIUS	AQUARIUS Call System will be promoted for uptake by other EU projects for transnational access to integrated research infrastructures.	INTERACT (INPA) AWI
WP4	Integration and management of multiple Infrastructures across TA	Lessons learned conveyed in report (D4.4) and Policy Brief (D7.7).	MI SSBE
WP7	Vision for marine research infrastructures of the future	Policy Brief (D7.7) and legacy video (D7.5) addressing the science-to-policy interface and bringing key messages to policy and decision makers, including recommendations towards the EU Green Deal Data Space.	SSBE

Table 4.1: Overview of potential AQUARIUS KERs

5. Mapping the Exploitation Pathway

The identified KERs will be followed up by the partners in Task 7.3, namely MARIS with support of MI, AWI, OGS, and SSBE. They will complete the exploitation plan templates in Annex 1 and 2 for each of the KERs. Annex 1 gives the template for KERS from the AQUARIUS project itself, while Annex 2 gives the template for KERS from the TA research projects.

These will be completed in dialogue with the PIs of the TA research projects and with leaders and/or partners of relevant Work Packages. This will be done in steps during the project duration. For the TA research projects, an initial step will be set once the TA project contracts have been signed, and this may be combined with the coaching and training by assigned expert data centres that will start at that given time. From that point onwards, TA project developments will be followed, and individual exploitation plans will be refined.

Developments for other project-related KERs will be followed in time and a dialogue will take place once there are sufficient results available. However, all project partners will be informed about the overall AQUARIUS exploitation strategy and the process for developing the final exploitation plan (D7.3).

The templates in Annex 1 and Annex 2 are aimed at developing an exploitation plan per KER according to the following criteria:

- General description of the KER?
- What existing challenge or issue does your KER address or deliver to?
- Who could use this KER and how? (What users would benefit from having access to this result/output and how). There could be more than one "user" in the "value chain".
- What channels will be used to reach these users? (meetings, webinars, workshop, open science platforms, EU data infrastructures).
- How would you measure "success" in terms of the use of your KER (monitoring KPI).
- Any other relevant suggestions.

6. AQUARIUS Intellectual Property Strategy

AQUARIUS implements an Open Data and Open Science policy. It is expected that the majority of KER arising from AQUARIUS and its funded TA projects will be in the form of reports, guidelines, data, research outputs, etc, which will all be (or have already been) made Open Access via appropriate platforms (website, Zenodo, European data infrastructure).

As derived from the Horizon Europe Grant Agreement and as stated in the AQUARIUS consortium agreement: AQUARIUS acknowledges the importance of Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) and its proper treatment. Relevant IPR will be identified previous to the Project start, in the Consortium Agreement.

The AQUARIUS Project Intellectual Property Policy as noted in the Consortium Agreement includes the following general rules, principles and recommendations towards the Collaboration: Each AQUARIUS partner owns the IP of outputs they created; and the consortium will (non- exclusively) manage and exploit the IP for the benefit of the project.

As for licensing, the Policy will envision that, when permitted by the licence terms and conditions applied, IP for relevant items will be licensed under an open-source licence.

In terms of joint ownerships, results are owned by the partner that generates them. Joint ownerships apply if: a) specific partners have jointly generated a result and b) it is not possible to establish the respective contribution of each beneficiary or separate them for the purpose of applying for, obtaining or maintaining their protection.

Unless otherwise agreed, each of the joint owners shall be entitled to use their jointly owned results for non-commercial research activities on a royalty-free basis, and without requiring the prior consent of the other joint owner(s), and; each of the joint owners shall be entitled to otherwise exploit the jointly owned results and to grant a nonexclusive licence to third parties (without any right to sub-licence), if the other joint owners are given at least 45 calendar days advance notice; and fair and reasonable compensation.

Additional, relevant IP management considerations will be further identified in the TA agreements signed with the awarded TA projects and included in their respective exploitation plans, which will be captured in the final Exploitation Plan (D7.3).

7. Example Exploitation Plan for direct AQUARIUS KER - AQUARIUS Data Gaps Report

The following plan has been developed as an example following the template in Annex 1.

Key exploitable result:	Please describe the output you identify as a KER. The AQUARIUS Data Gaps report represents a comprehensive analysis of existing data gaps in relation to knowledge targets of the Mission Ocean and Waters and the European Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership.
	What solution does it offer or what problem does it address? It will ensure that data collection efforts by the TA projects are targeted and deliver meaningful data to advance the goals of the Mission Ocean and Waters and the SBEP targets.
Target users:	Who can use this result and how? (There may be more than one type of user, and these may be at various levels in the value chain. Please describe all) User 1: Those designing the TA calls - to ensure that data collection is targeted. User 2: The SBEP, to formulate their own Calls. User 3: DG MARE/DG RTD - to inform the design of future funding calls to ensure data collection is targeted towards the Mission goals.
Dissemination channel	How can you reach the target user? User 1: Direct partner to partner contact. User 2: Structuring activities in Task 1.3

	User 3: Key conclusions and recommendations will be taken up in the AQUARIUS policy brief which will be presented to relevant policy contacts at a dedicated event at the end of the AQUARIUS project. E.g.
Impact	What change would result from the use of your result? Important data-gaps are filled resulting in better informed decision making.
	How could you measure success or uptake of your result? Number of TA projects providing new data relevant to the gaps identified. Number of other projects/funding proposals referencing the report. Number of policy makers attending final event.

8. Impact

The AQUARIUS project will provide innovative, and customised, and highly efficient research infrastructure services aimed at enhancing and increasing society's long-term and consistent problem-solving capacity and evidence-based policy making. There are multiple factors and activities to ensure that the AQUARIUS project will achieve a maximum impact.

- The project will integrate 57 world class research infrastructures, and associated services, and involve leading experts from 45 organisations, working with stakeholders who are keenly aware and knowledgeable about the urgent challenges for our oceans and waters.
- The AQUARIUS project design will ensure that at least 10 excellent projects will be realised through the AQUARIUS RI services. The Access Calls are specifically designed, through consultation with expert stakeholders, to address clean oceans and waters. The dedicated outreach programme and campaigning will attract researchers who will recognise the new opportunities available through the RI services. Scientific excellence will be the hallmark of the funded AQUARIUS TA research projects, due to the peer review process.
- An open data strategy and open science practices will be promoted and pursued as a high priority.

Open Data Strategy Overview: A dedicated Data Management approach (D6.2) will be implemented by a team of experienced Data Centres, aimed at ensuring that collected and generated metadata and data become part of the European data (management) infrastructures for long term stewardship and wide access and use. The approach includes several components such as:

- Formulating and reviewing Data Management Plans (DMPs) per TA research project.
- Educating and training TA research project scientific teams in using FAIR data management standards and associated tools and services for sharing and ingesting their TA metadata and data in the prescribed data management infrastructures.
- Coaching and supporting TA scientific teams before, during, and after the TA projects for achieving ingestion of their data results.

- Setting up and maintaining feeding the online AQUARIUS Dataflow Dashboard (ADD), giving up-to-date information on the data flow progress per TA project and giving access to the metadata, data, and data products as achieved.

Open Analytical Services Overview: The scientific teams of each TA project will be invited to make use of the Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment (VRE), which hosts a range of analytical software services, Virtual Labs, and a framework for developing new VLabs as analytical pipelines. Including services for FAIR documenting (provenance metadata), visualizing, and publishing of the analytical data products in a product catalogue which is shared with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

TA scientists will be trained and experience web-based open science practices, coached by VRE experts. They can elaborate their new data sets by deeper analyses and by combining these with existing data collections from major European data repositories. This extra dimension is made possible through a synergy with the EU Blue-Cloud 2026 project.

The data, data product and knowledge outcomes and the closer cooperation between RI's will contribute to the goals of the Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030", European Green Deal and international climate initiatives, as these are central themes and priorities within the AQUARIUS Project.

Annex 1 - KER Pathway Template for Project Partners

Key exploitable result:	Please describe the output you identify as a KER? E.g.
	What solution does it offer or what problem does it address? E.g.
Target users:	Who can use this result and how? E.g.
Dissemination channel:	How can you reach the target user? E.g.
Impact:	What change would result from the use of your result? E.g.
	What difference would it make and to whom? E.g. How could you measure this? E.g.

Annex 2 - KER Pathway Template for TA Projects

Key exploitable result (KER):	<p>Please describe the main results/outputs of your project?</p> <p>These could take the form of data, new scientific knowledge in the form of a paper, recommendations for policy developers, new or improved technological innovation.</p> <p>KER1: KER2: KER3:</p>
	<p>What solution does the KER offer or what problem does it address?</p> <p>KER1: KER2: KER3:</p>
Target users:	<p>Who can use these results and how?</p> <p>KER1: KER2: KER3:</p>
Dissemination channel:	<p>How can you reach the target user?</p> <p>KER1: KER2: KER3:</p>
Impact:	<p>What change would result from the use of your result?</p> <p>KER1: KER2: KER3:</p>
	<p>What difference would it make and to whom?</p> <p>How could you measure this?</p> <p>KER1: KER2: KER3:</p>